

Thiopegan Derivatives. Part XXXIII

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6,7-Methylenedioxy-2,10-disubstituted-4,11-thiopega-9-enes have been synthesised by condensing 6-*N*-acylamino-piperonal with β -mercaptoethylamines or their hydrochlorides in presence of sodium acetate. That the thiazolidine ring is formed prior to the quinazoline one is supported by isolation of the intermediate 2-(2'-*N*-acetylamino-4', 5'-methylenedioxyphenyl)thiazolidine, in the condensation of 6-*N*-acetylamino-piperonal with β -mercaptoethylamine, and its conversion to 6,7-methylenedioxy-10-methyl-4,11-thiopega-9-ene. The condensation of 6-*N*-ethoxycarbonylamino-piperonal with β -mercaptoethylamines affords only 2-(2'-*N*-ethoxycarbonylamino-4',5'-methylenedioxyphenyl)thiazolidines, cyclisation of which could not be accomplished. Attempts in obtaining the latter product by treatment of 2-(2'-amino-4',5'-methylenedioxyphenyl) thiazolidine with ethyl chloroformate also have so far met with failure.

In continuation of our previous communication¹ regarding the syntheses of the derivatives of 4, 11-thiopegans (I) we herein report in detail the synthetic routes pursued.

6,7-Methylenedioxy-4,11-thiopega-10-methyl-9-ene (I: R = H; R' = Me) and its 3-methoxycarbonyl and 3-ethoxycarbonyl derivatives (I: R = OCOME; R' = Me and I: R = OCOEt; R' = Me) have been synthesised by condensing 6-*N*-acetylamino-piperonal (II: R' = Me) with β -mercaptoethylamine (III: R = H) and the hydrochlorides of methyl and ethyl esters of (—)-cysteine (III: R = OCOME or OCOEt). The latter two condensations were carried out in presence of sodium acetate. A probable mechanism is shown below.

Likewise, 6,7-methylenedioxy-4,11-thiopega-10-phenyl-9-ene (I: R' = Ph; R = H) has been obtained from 6-*N*-benzoylaminopiperonal (II) and β -mercaptoethylamine (vide Table I).

That the thiazolidine ring is formed prior to the quinazoline one is supported by the fact that in the condensation of 6-*N*-acetylamino-piperonal (II: R' = Me) and β -mercaptoethylamine (III: R = H), the intermediate 2-(2'-acetylamino-4,5-methylenedioxyphenyl)-thiazolidine (IV: R = H; R' = Me), m.p. 156-57°, was isolated along with (I: R = H; R' = Me), m.p. 178°. This intermediate on heating in ethanol cyclised to furnish the product, m.p. 178°.

With a view to synthesising 6,7-methylenedioxy-4,11-thiopega-10-one (VII: R = H), 6-*N*-ethoxycarbonylamino-piperonal (V) was condensed with β -mercaptoethylamine (III: R = H); but it furnished 2'-(2'-*N*-ethoxycarbonylamino)-4',5'-methylenedioxyphenyl-thiazolidine (VI: R = H).

Attempts at cyclisation of (VI) by heating in (i) diphenyl ether as well as liquid paraffin and heating at 110° under vacuum (1 mm) and (ii) ethanol in presence of protonic reagents like HCl did not succeed. In the case of (ii), the thiazolidine ring, however, underwent fission and furnished (V).

Likewise, the condensations of (V) with the hydrochlorides of the methyl and ethyl esters of (—)-cysteine (III: R = OCOMe or/COEt) in presence of sodium acetate furnished the corresponding thiazolidine derivatives (VI) (Table II).

An alternative route pursued for the synthesis of 6,7-methylenedioxy-4,11-thiopega-10-one (VII: R = H) is noted below. But here the attempted cyclisation of 2-(2'-amino-4',5'-methylenedioxyphenyl)thiazolidine (VIII), obtained by condensing 6-aminopiperonal with β -mercaptoethylamine by treating with ethyl chloroformate, furnished

6-*N*-ethoxycarbonylamino piperonal (II: R' = OEt) and not (VII: R = H).

EXPERIMENTAL

1. 10-Methyl- or 10-Phenyl-6,7-methylenedioxy-4,11-thiopega-9-ene (I: R = Me or Ph; R = H)

(a). *Condensation of β -Mercaptoethylamine (III: R = H) with 6-*N*-Acetylamino piperonal (II: R' = Me): Isolation of (2'-Acetylamino-4,5-methylenedioxyphenyl)thiazolidine (IV: R' = Me; R = H) and Formation of 10-methyl-6,7-methylenedioxy-4, 11-thiopega-9-ene (I: R = H; R' = Me).*—Dry H₂S gas was passed through a solution of ethyleneimine (1.3 g., 1.0 *M*) in anhydrous ethanol (30 ml) for 3 hr. and a solution of 6-*N*-acetylamino piperonal (6.2 g., 1 *M*) in ethanol (20 ml) was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 15 min. and kept overnight when a white solid separated. This was collected and crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 156-57°, yield 5 g. (62.5%). (Found: C, 54.31; H, 5.12; N, 10.82. C₁₂H₁₄O₃N₂S requires C, 54.13; H, 5.26; N, 10.52%).

The filtrate from above on dilution with water provided a white solid which was crystallised from ethanol in white needles, m.p. 178°. The product, m.p. 156-57°, was refluxed in ethanolic solution for 2 hr. On cooling, a solid separated which was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 178°, undepressed on admixture with the above sample.

(b). *Condensation of β -mercaptoethylamine (III: R = H) with 6-*N*-benzoylamino piperonal (II: R' = Ph)* was carried out in the same manner as in expt. (a).

(c). *Condensation of the Hydrochlorides of the Esters of (—)-cysteine (III: R = CO₂Me or CO₂Et) with 6-*N*-Acetylamino piperonal (II: R' = Me).*—6-*N*-Acetylamino piperonal (II: R' = Me) in ethanol was added to a solution of equivalent amounts of the hydrochlorides of the methyl or ethyl ester of (—)-cysteine and sodium acetate in water. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hr. and kept overnight. The product separating was collected and purified (Table I).

TABLE I

Synthesis of 10-methyl- and 10-phenyl-6,7-methylenedioxy-4,11-thiopega-9-enes (I).

S.No.	6- <i>N</i> -Acetylamino-piperonal(V) used (R')	β -Mercaptoethyl-amine used.	*Product (IV). R. R'.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1	Me	β -Mercaptoethyl-amine	H Me	178°	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂ S	C : 58.54% H : 5.12 N : 11.28	58.06% 4.84 11.29
2	Me	(—)-Cysteine hydrochloride	Me	168-70°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂ S	N : 9.61	9.15
3	Me	Do, methyl ester	CO ₂ Me Me	156°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	N : 9.13	8.75
4	Ph	β -Mercaptoethyl-amine	H Ph	187°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂ S	N : 9.66	9.03

*Crystallised from EtOH.

2. Formation of 2-(2'-Ethoxycarbonyl)-4',5'-methylenedioxyphenyl-thiazolidine (VI:R=H)

(a). 6-N-Ethoxycarbonylamino-piperonal.—To 6-aminopiperonal (16.5 g., 1*M*), dissolved in ethanol (20 ml), a solution of sodium carbonate (8.07 g., 1.5*M*) in water (30 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was set for refluxing and ethyl chloroformate (15 ml) was added in small amounts during 10 min. Separation of a yellow compound started after 20 min. It was refluxed for further 20 min. and cooled. The product was collected (17.5 g.) by filtration; the filtrate on dilution with water (100 ml) furnished more of the same product (2.5 g.). It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 133-35°. (Found : N, 6.4. C₁₁H₁₁O₃N requires N, 5.9%).

TABLE II

Synthesis of 2-(2'-amino-4,5-methylenedioxyphenyl)thiazolidine (VI).

S.No.	β -Mercaptoethylamine used.	Product (I) R.	Cryst. frcm.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1	β -Mercaptoethylamine	H	Acetone	156-57°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	C : 52.50% H : 5.05 S : 10.75	52.70% 5.40 10.81
2	(-)-Cysteine hydrochloride ethyl ester	CO ₂ Et	Ethanol	122°	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₂ S	C : 52.05 H : 5.10 N : 8.57 S : 8.25	52.17 5.43 8.04 8.69

(b). Condensation of β -Mercaptoethylamine (III: R=H) with (II:R'=OEt).—(i). A solution of (II: R'=OEt) (2.5 g., 1.0*M*) in ethanol (20 ml) was mixed with a solution of β -mercaptoethylamine (III: R=H) (0.75 g., 1.0*M*) in ethanol (10 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 30 min. on a water bath and kept overnight. The slightly yellowish compound, thus obtained, was crystallised from acetone in white needles, changing colour to yellow on standing; m.p. 156-57°.

(ii). Alternatively, the same product was obtained by refluxing the solution of 6-N-ethoxycarbonylamino-piperonal (II: R'=OEt) (7.9 g., 1.0*M*) with β -mercaptoethylamine (III: R=H), produced *in situ* by passing dry H₂S gas in a solution of ethyleneimine (2.5g., 1.0*M*) in anhydrous ethanol (30 ml) for 3 hr. and keeping overnight.

(c). Condensations of the hydrochlorides of the esters of (-)-cysteine (III: R=CO₂Et or CO₂Me) with (II: R=OEt) were carried out by a procedure similar to the one adopted in expt 1(c).

(d). Attempted Cyclisation of 2-(2'-N-Ethoxycarbonylamino-4,5-methylenedioxyphenyl)-4-ethoxycarbonylthiazolidine (VI: R=O.COEt).—Compound (VI) was heated in an oil bath at 150° and the product was crystallised from anhydrous ethanol, m.p. 133°, undepressed on admixture with *o*-ethoxycarbonylamino-piperonal.

Compound(VI) (1g.) was heated in vacuum (1 mm) at 100-110° for 2 hr. Some vapours condensed on the cooler part of the flask. On crystallisation from ethanol, a sticky mass separated, which could not be characterised.

3. 2-(2'-Amino-4',5'-methylenedioxyphenyl)thiazolidine (VIII)

(a). A solution of 6-aminopiperonal (6 g., 1*M*) in ethanol (30 ml) was mixed with a solution of β -mercaptoethylamine (25 g., 1*M*) in ethanol (10 ml); the mixed solution was triturated well and allowed to stand at the room temperature for 3 hr. On cooling, the yellow solid separating was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 177-78°, yield 4g. (48.2%).

(b). Dry H₂S was passed through a solution of ethyleneimine (2.2g., 1*M*) in anhydrous ethanol (20 ml) in cold for 3 hr. A solution of 6-aminopiperonal (8.5 g., 1*M*) in ethanol (20 ml) was then added. After keeping for 3 hr., it was cooled. The yellow compound separating was collected and crystallised from ethyl acetate in yellow needles, m.p. 177-78°, yield 6.5 g. (56.03%). It did not depress the m.p. of the above sample (i) on admixture. (N, 12.96. C₁₀H₁₁O₂N₂S requires N, 12.5%).

4. Attempted Formation of 6,7-Methylenedioxy-4,11-thiopega-10-one (VII: R=H)

(a). Compound (VIII) was heated with an equivalent amount of ethyl chloroformate. The product obtained was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 133°, undepressed on admixture with 6-*N*-ethoxycarbonylamino-piperonal.

(b). Alternatively, (VIII) was heated with an equivalent amount of acetic anhydride. The product obtained was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 160°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample of 6-*N*-acetylamino-piperonal.